

Towards safer mobility

A holistic approach to tackling violence in public transportation

Insights and policy recommendations from the ACCTING project

February 2025

Safe public transport is essential for reaching a socially just and inclusive green transition. Only when people feel safe on buses, subways, trains, etc., more people will be willing to switch from car usage to public transport. However, violence in public transport remains pervasive, with disproportionate negative effects on operating staff, women, and socially vulnerable groups. Global comparisons show that 3 out of 5 women report experiencing sexual harassment on public transport (Social Development Direct), and in some cases 4 in 5 young women (Hooker et al). This is more than two times what women experience in society at large (FRA, EIGE, Eurostat (2024)).

Public transport operators, key players in preventing and addressing violence, are also victims of it. Every major public transport operator is confronted every day with violence against staff, which has major consequences on people and on the quality and reliability of the service offered. Thus, the overall prevalence of violence discourages the use of public transport, contributes to an increased reliance on private vehicles, and it forces individuals to accept unsafe conditions or restrict their mobility.

This factsheet provides evidence-based recommendations to guide policymakers and operators in fostering safer and more inclusive public transport systems, leveraging insights from the EU-funded ACCTING project and advocating for the use of the UniSAFE 7P framework.

Recommendations

The UniSAFE¹ 7P model provides a structured and systemic approach to understand and tackle gender-based violence. This model has been applied in various contexts, e.g. research and higher education, and sports, covering violence as a continuum and in a holistic way. By applying this successful model in the context of public transport, looking at the entire journey of the user from door-to-door, both transportation providers and policymakers can develop more effective and comprehensive strategies to ensure safe and accessible mobility for all users. Based on successful case studies and research, examples of potential measures that can be taken within each “P” to start tackling violence in transportation are provided

below. These examples provide a starting point for an open discussion involving their local stakeholders and partners to design their own, tailored action plan.

1. Prevalence: Understanding the extent and nature of the violence

Transport data reveals a gap in safety monitoring. The lack of specifically gender-disaggregated data and ineffective reporting systems hampers efforts to address the issue. Recommendations include:

- Conduct regular, participatory safety audits involving diverse user groups to identify high-risk areas, times, and patterns.
- Create user-friendly and accessible reporting mechanisms, such as apps or hotlines, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality.
- Introduce surveys to assess underreporting and refine reporting mechanisms.
- Establish mandatory gender-segregated data collection systems for transport operators.

¹ [UniSAFE D3.1 Theoretical and conceptual framework](#)

2. Prevention: Implementing measures to stop violence before it occurs

- Redesign infrastructure to enhance safety, including improved lighting, clear sightlines, and visible CCTV systems.
- Include gender-sensitivity training in mandatory curricula for all transport and subcontracted staff.
- Launch zero-tolerance public awareness campaigns targeting both potential perpetrators and bystanders to encourage intervention.
- Implement request-stop programmes during off-peak hours to minimise exposure to unsafe environments.

3. Protection: Ensuring safety and support for victims and bystanders

- Increase the visible presence of trained security personnel, especially during high-risk times.
- Equip stations and vehicles with panic buttons and emergency call systems linked to rapid response teams.
- Ensure access to 24/7 helplines staffed by trained professionals to assist victims and witnesses.

4. Prosecution: Taking legal and disciplinary action against perpetrators

- Establish clear protocols for first responders and judicial processes to ensure swift action against perpetrators.
- Develop specialised gender-based violence units within existing transport police or security teams.
- Deploy technology such as body cameras and evidence collection tools to strengthen cases and improve judicial outcomes.

5. Provision of services: Offering support services for victims and survivors

- Offer immediate psychological support and legal aid through trained staff or external partnerships.
- Create advocacy programmes to help victims navigate legal and recovery processes.
- Provide workplace support services for transport workers facing violence, including trauma counselling.

6. Partnerships: Cooperating with relevant stakeholders and organisations

- Facilitate collaboration between transport operators, law enforcement, NGOs, and community organisations to align interventions.
- Engage local governments and advocacy groups to co-design transport safety policies and initiatives.
- Partner with educational institutions to develop inclusive urban mobility training programmes.

7. Policies: Developing comprehensive strategies and formal commitments

- Establish uniform minimum safety standards across transport modes, ensuring consistent implementation.
- Require operators to include safety clauses in procurement contracts, including staff training and infrastructure upgrades.
- Enact comprehensive national and regional policies explicitly addressing gender-based violence in transportation.

Better Stories

FRANCE

Île-de-France: Comprehensive Safety Initiatives

In 2018, the Île-de-France region launched a multi-pronged approach to reduce harassment and improve public transport safety. Key measures included:

- **Security:** Deployment of 785 specifically trained security agents and increased patrols during vulnerable hours.
- **Emergency Systems:** Introduction of a streamlined alert hotline (3117) and visible emergency call points in stations.
- **Innovative Services:** Piloting a "stop-on-request" service after 22:00 on bus routes to minimise walking distances at night.
- **Public Campaigns:** An extensive awareness drive encouraged bystander intervention and emphasised zero tolerance for harassment. The programme has since been integrated into long-term infrastructure investment plans, solidifying its impact.

Find out more: <https://charter-equality.eu/exemple-de-bonnes-pratiques/ile-de-france-public-transport-anti-harassment-campaign.html>

SPAIN

Barcelona: Improving safety for women through collective action

The feminist collective Col·lectiu Punt 6 has spearheaded transformative safety measures:

- **Participatory Audits:** Women-led exploratory walks and bike rides identified safety risks and accessibility challenges.
- **Actionable Data:** Recommendations from these audits informed the redesign of the Bicipia bike network and enhanced station safety for the local operator FGC.
- **Capacity Building:** Training programmes for urban planners and officials now embed gender perspectives in public space design. This grassroots initiative demonstrates the power of collaborative urban planning to address systemic gender inequities.

Find out more: <https://blogs.amb.cat/mobilitat/ca/2021/04/21/entrevista-a-la-mirada-feminista/>

Italo: Proactive Safety and Training

Private train operator Italo implemented wide-ranging safety measures through partnerships and training:

- Collaboration: Partnership with the railway police ensured uniformed officers were present on trains, fostering passenger and crew confidence.
- Empowering Staff: Self-defence and de-escalation training, conducted with Telefono Rosa, has equipped over 1,000 employees to handle and prevent incidents effectively.
- Focus on Inclusivity: Training expanded beyond women's safety to address broader threats, creating a safer environment for all passengers and staff.

Find out more: <https://italospa.italotreno.it/ufficio-stampa/comunicati-stampa/italo-al-via-il-nuovo-progetto-con-la-collaborazione-della-polizia-ferroviaria.html>

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About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

Running until May 2025 and based on two research cycles, ACCTING mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies.

Find out more about the project and discover more factsheets at <https://accting.eu>

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Authorship and contributions

Authors: Arne Nys (YW), Marina Cacace (K&I), Alain Denis (YW).

Contributors: YW, ECSA, and contributions from the ACCTING consortium.

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